

EXPLORATION AND DEVELOPMENT SIGNIFICANCE OF POST-PERMIAN FOLDING AND FRACTURING WITHIN THE PERMIAN BASIN

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ABSTRACT

Many of the largest Permian Basin fields are associated with folding that appears to be post-Permian in age, the result of early Tertiary reactivation of deeper fault blocks. The processes of differential compaction and drape over paleotopography are not sufficient to explain the larger folds.

The Wasson San Andres field is a good example of a commercially important post-Permian fold. Study of Wasson depositional facies indicates that there was no topographic high in the area of the structural crest during San Andres time. This rules out drape over pre-existing topography as a cause for the structural high. There is evidence for differential compaction at Wasson, but compactional thinning over the structural crest reduced the height of the structure. Therefore, compaction could not have produced the structure. The best hypothesis is that the folding formed as a result of reactivation of deeper faults. This reactivation was probably part of the early Tertiary Laramide orogeny.

San Andres dolomites on the structural crest of Wasson are fractured. Vertical uplift of fault blocks when the San Andres reached its maximum burial could have added additional vertical stress to the overburden pressure, producing localized areas of elevated pore pressure within the San Andres. Such increased pore pressure may have been sufficient to allow fracturing to occur as a result of northeasterly-directed Laramide compression.

Reservoir development is affected by localized fracturing of San Andres and Clearfork strata. Fracturing provides locally-enhanced permeability that can have different production characteristics such as higher primary recovery and early water breakthrough during secondary recovery.

Reactivation of Pennsylvanian faults has significant implications for pre-Woodford structural plays and for the Pennsylvanian and Early Permian synorogenic detrital reservoirs. The orientation of the pre-Tertiary structural grain has a primary control on how individual fault blocks were reactivated. Northwesterly-trending faults had reactivation that was dominantly vertical so

large anticlinal folds formed in the overlying, unfaulted section. Such large anticlinal reservoirs were found early in the exploration history of the Permian Basin. Reactivation of easterly-trending fault zones, however, probably produced movement with a strike-slip component and less vertical uplift. These zones have complex structure with numerous small fault blocks. Much of the future potential in the pre-Woodford plays lies in areas such as these where 3-D seismic can be used to image these small but profitable traps.

INTRODUCTION

There are at least 3.5 billion barrels of recoverable oil trapped in San Andres reservoirs that have significant four-way structural closure (Galloway et al., 1983). For many of these fields the age of the folding is clearly post-Permian. The best hypothesis for the origin of these folds is that they formed in response to Laramide reactivation of deeper faults (Winfree, 1994; 1995a). Early Tertiary uplift of the deeper fault blocks forced the overlying unfaulted section to fold into domes and anticlines with relatively low dips. Such post-Permian folding increased the height of the traps so thicker oil columns accumulated.

This paper will present evidence for post-Permian folding of the San Andres and discuss the economic significance of this relatively young deformation. Recognition of the age and structural style of this episode of folding provides a set of new ideas that can be applied to exploration and development work in many plays within the Permian Basin.

FOLDING AND FRACTURING OF THE WASSON SAN ANDRES FIELD

Background

The Wasson San Andres field of Gaines and Yoakum Counties (Figure 1) lies on the Northwestern Shelf of the Midland Basin. It is a combined structural/stratigraphic trap and the highest point of the field is the Denver Dome (Figure 2).

The San Andres in the study area consists of a series of late Leonardian and early Guadalupian dolomitized

FIGURE 1. Folds involving Leonardian and younger rocks of the Permian Basin. W = Wasson field, S = Seminole field, M = Mabee field, HG = Howard-Glasscock field, GEL = Giddings Estate Lease, PR = Pembrook Unit, Y = Yates Field, BM = Barrilla Mountains (modified from Winfree, 1992).

carbonate ramps that prograded southward into the Midland Basin. San Andres strata were first described by Lee and Girty (1909) in the San Andres Mountains in Sierra County, New Mexico. Kottowski et al. (1956) and Lindsay (1994) have provided additional useful detail in the area of the type section. Ramondetta's (1982a, 1982b) regional studies of the San Andres of the Northwestern Shelf establish a useful framework to understand the setting of Wasson.

Proposed Origin of San Andres Folds

Ramondetta's (1982b) regional San Andres structure maps (Figure 3) illustrate how the Denver Dome is an anomaly on the Northwestern Shelf. Structurally, the Northwest Shelf has gentle southeasterly dips of about 0.3 degrees on the Pi marker. The Pi marker is a silty dolomite bed that can be correlated all around the Northwestern Shelf so it forms a reliable structural marker. In places, there are monoclines with dips up to about 1 degree. The steepest monocline overlies the Wolfcampian shelf margin with dips up to 2 degrees. The Denver Dome merges with the shelf-margin monocline on its eastern and southern flanks. Dips on the flanks range from 1 to 2 degrees. These folds involve the post-San Andres section at least as high as the Yates Formation (Figure 4).

At Wasson, there is no correlation of San Andres lithofacies and present-day structure. Distribution of lithofacies indicates that the Denver Dome did not exist during San Andres time. Detailed description of over

3000 feet of San Andres core in the Exxon-operated Cornell Unit (Winfrey, 1995b) and published studies from other areas of Wasson (Mathis, 1986; Bent, 1992) also indicate that the depositional surface had almost no paleotopographic relief. The Cornell Unit lies on the flank of the Denver Dome and present-day structural dip is northerly (Figure 2). Original depositional dip was southeasterly into the Midland Basin. This indicates that the Denver Dome could not have formed as result of drape over paleotopography that existed during San Andres time. One must conclude that the Denver Dome formed in post-San Andres time.

There is evidence of thinning in the Yates to base of San Andres interval. The amount of thinning correlates well with structural elevation of the Pi marker (Figure 5). Detailed correlations suggest that this thinning is not due to depositional onlap of a paleotopographic high because individual beds appear to correlate across the thinned area. The area of thinning coincides with the crest of the Denver Dome so it seems that differential compaction has occurred over the fold. The effect of this compaction is to reduce the structural relief. If the compaction effects are removed the closure would have greater height, so differential compaction could not have caused the structural relief.

Evidence of compaction is abundant in the Cornell Unit cores where San Andres strata are folded. Large stylolites with amplitudes in excess of 5 cm are present and lower-amplitude stylolites typically occur in every foot of the mud-rich facies. However, unfolded areas of the Northwestern Shelf appear to have undergone much less compaction. Stylolites are rare in Exxon's cores from a correlative interval of the San Andres in the Slaughter-Lelleveld field (Coons lease, Hockley County, Texas). Published studies from other parts of Slaughter-Lelleveld (Ebanks, 1990; Dulaney and Hadik, 1990) also do not report stylolites. This suggests that the Denver Dome area may have undergone a greater degree of compaction. Unfortunately, the author did not have access to any Wasson cores that were not on the Denver Dome so this hypothesis could not be tested directly. Ramondetta's (1982b) regional isopachs show that Wasson lies within a regional San Andres thin. The regional thin roughly correlates with the area of the underlying Wolfcampian shelf-margin carbonate buildups.

Post-Guadalupian uplift of fault blocks below the Wolfcampian buildups could have produced the area of greater compaction and the forced folds in the San Andres. Horak's (1985) burial history curve (Figure 6) indicates that the Guadalupian section

Figure 2. Top of San Andres structure, Wasson field, Gaines and Yoakum Counties, Texas. Contour interval is 100 feet.

reached maximum burial just before uplift began at the beginning of the Tertiary. If the deeper fault blocks below Wasson were uplifted at that time they would have added increased vertical stress to that caused by the overburden. If this scenario is true, compaction would occur only in those areas of uplift so that thinning would correlate with structural highs.

Folding of the San Andres by differential compaction of the underlying section around the Wolfcampian buildups is an unlikely alternative hypothesis. First, the pattern of thinning over the San Andres highs persists below the San Andres. If the Denver Dome formed by a passive lowering of the flank areas by differential compaction, the section would be thinner off the structural crest. Second, an amount of differential compaction sufficient to produce the present structural relief would require a major change in Wolfcampian lithofacies across the area of the Denver Dome. Such important lithofacies contrasts do exist south and east of the Denver Dome so differential compaction could have increased dips in that area. However the change in lithofacies to the west and north are probably very gradual so differential compaction in the section underlying the San Andres would have had minimal influence on present structure. Additional work in areas of deep well control, however, is needed before this hypothesis can be conclusively rejected.

Fracturing of the San Andres

The San Andres is only locally fractured. Most interpretations of San Andres core data (Bebout and Harris, 1990) do not report significant fracturing. However, fracturing seems to be more common where the San Andres has been folded.

Cores from the Cornell Unit contain many open natural fractures which are oil-stained and occasionally mineralized. There is no orientation data for these fractures. Chuber and

Figure 3. Regional structure of the Pi marker (modified from Ramondetta, 1982b).

Figure 4. Schematic cross section of the Guadalupian section of the Wasson field. Six wells were used to construct this section. Location of section in Figure 9. Vertical exaggeration is 8.6X.

Figure 5. Plot of thickness of the Yates to base of San Andres interval vs. structural elevation. Each point represents one well on the Denver Dome.

Pusey (1985) also report San Andres fractures from the Reeves field. Reeves field production is from folded San Andres strata just southeast of Wasson.

Orientation data also does exist for San Andres fractures at the Vacuum field of Lea County, New Mexico (approximately 35 miles southwest of Wasson). Purves (1990) reported orientations of N60°E and N65°E for the interval from 1000 to 9000 feet, which includes the San Andres. There is significant folding of the San Andres in the Vacuum field. This orientation is parallel to the Laramide maximum compression direction so the fractures may have formed at the same time as those of the Spraberry (Winfree, 1994; 1995a).

Vertical stresses that produced forced folding and compaction during uplift may have produced localized areas of elevated pore pressure within the San Andres. At the time of uplift, the San Andres would have been under maximum overburden. The addition of vertical stress during uplift could have raised pore pressure enough to allow fractures to form parallel to the Laramide principle stress direction in the manner postulated by Lorenz et al. (1991). If that is true, areas that have undergone forced folding in the San Andres may be fractured while surrounding areas remain undeformed.

OTHER SAN ANDRES FIELDS WITH FOLDS

There are several other San Andres traps which appear to be controlled, at least in part, by forced folds. The regional significance of this post-Permian deformation will be discussed with the following examples. These fields have not been thoroughly studied by the author so forced folding is only inferred.

Horvath and Miller (1994) published a cross section (Figure 7) from the Mabee San Andres field (Figure 1) that clearly shows post-San Andres folding. The facies relationships indicate that the originally very low-angle depositional surfaces have been folded into a series of anticlines and synclines.

The Howard-Glasscock field (Figure 1) is another possible post-Guadalupian forced fold that produces from the San Andres. It is significant for two reasons. First, if it is a forced fold, its location on the Eastern Shelf margin would indicate that uplift occurred across the entire width of the Midland Basin. Second, Howard-Glasscock is at the eastern end of an aligned trend of low-relief folds that produce from the San Andres or Grayburg sections. This trend extends westward from Howard-Glasscock across Glasscock

Figure 6. Burial history curves for the Permian Basin region (from Horak, 1985).

County into Midland County to include the McDowell, Zant, Germania, Azalea, and Brazos fields. Such a structural alignment suggests that a large-scale deeper zone of weakness was re-activated in post-Guadalupean time.

The Atlas of Major Texas Oil Reservoirs (Galloway et al., 1983) illustrates several other large San Andres or Grayburg fields that have significant folds. The biggest of these are Emma, Goldsmith, Mabee, Means, Midland Farms, Sand Hills, Seminole, and Waddell. Estimated ultimate recoveries for these fields is a combined 1.5 billion barrels of oil. The 2 billion barrels of recoverable oil in the Yates San Andres field are trapped in a dome that is expressed at the surface in Cretaceous rocks (Berger et al., 1992). The Yates dome is almost certainly a Laramide fold (Winfree, 1994, 1995a).

ECONOMIC SIGNIFICANCE

The imprint of post-Guadalupean compressive stresses in the Midland Basin region has economically significant implications. This is true of not only the San Andres but to many other important plays. Winfree (1994, 1995a) presented the implications of Laramide fracturing on the Spraberry. The reactivation of deeper faults may have influenced the formation of traps in the

pre-Woodford structural plays. If the fracturing extends to surface rocks in some areas, there may be important implications for ground water as well.

Exploration for Small San Andres Fields

The trend of small San Andres fields extending west from Howard-Glasscock mentioned above may not be unique. The GMK-Cedar Lake trend of Gaines County is probably another example. The major barrier to exploration of these small fields is the difficulty of accurately imaging low-relief San Andres structures coupled with the low average per-well recoveries. These fields can be profitable, however, if dry holes are minimized in exploration and development. Acquisition of 3-D seismic could be targeted to exploit these trends and to reduce dry-hole risk.

Correspondence of San Andres Folds and Fractures: Implications for Clearfork Fields

Most published studies concerning the management of San Andres fields (Bebout and Harris, 1990) do not emphasize the role of fractures. This is partly due to a lack of significant fractures in many San Andres fields and partly due to a lack of data. If the uplift that folded the San Andres also provided the extra stress to produce

Figure 7. Structural cross section of San Andres pay at the Mabee field of Andrews and Martin Counties (from Horvath and Miller, 1994). Note folding of originally flat supratidal layer at the top of zone 1.

the San Andres also provided the extra stress to produce the fractures, then one must ask if every fold within the San Andres is also fractured. Obviously, there must be a minimum threshold depth of burial before uplift could cause the fractures, so some folded San Andres rocks probably remain unfractured (Figure 8). Even where the San Andres has been folded but not fractured, it seems reasonable to expect that the deeper Clearfork section would be fractured.

Given the generally low permeability of the San Andres and Clearfork dolomites, the presence of fractures can make a significant impact on reservoir performance. Many of these fields show evidence of anisotropic horizontal permeability with a preferred east-west orientation.

Secondary and Tertiary recovery can be greatly affected by fracture-related permeability, especially where operating plans do not consider the existence of fractures. Wells with significant fracture permeability may have drained larger areas during primary production thus the remaining oil may be less than calculated. During enhanced recovery operations, these same wells may also be plagued by water- or CO₂-breakthrough problems. These patterns may not be economical to flood so recognition of this problem could lead to reductions in operating costs per barrel produced. If areas of greater fracture intensity could be correlated to deeper structural features as they can in the Spraberry (Winfrey, 1994; 1995a), an operator could design a more-efficient and cost-effective development strategy.

Possibilities for New Fractured Play: Lower Wolfcamp Shale

The reactivation of the fault zones in post-Permian time creates a complex pattern of deformation in the uppermost Pennsylvanian and lower Wolfcampian rocks. Presumably, these rocks were unfaulted or only slightly offset by faults at the close of Wolfcampian time. The reactivation would produce new faulting and relatively intense folding near the fault zone. It is logical to con-

clude that these rocks may be highly fractured near reactivated fault zones. Throughout most of the Midland Basin these rocks are highly organic shales that are known to be source rocks. It is possible that a fractured shale play exists in these areas and has been overlooked. Although it is hard to imagine that any play has been overlooked in the Midland Basin, remember that most deep wells are not drilled into fault zones. They are usually drilled significantly away from the fault zone to test a fault-independent closure. Dry holes drilled near reactivated fault zones may be worth a second look. Areas with significant oil shows may warrant horizontal drilling perpendicular to fractures.

Exploration for Deeper Prospects Below Post-Permian Folds

If the presence of a Post-Permian fold indicates uplift of the underlying section, then the geometry of the fold probably provides useful information about deeper prospects. The anticlinal fold over the San Andres at Seminole field is a direct indication of the underlying topography of the Wolfcampian and Leonardian carbonate buildups (Figure 9). The crest of the buildup underlies the crest of the San Andres high. However, the

Figure 8 Schematic cross section to illustrate the proposed mechanism to develop localized areas of fractured San Andres and Clearfork strata. The combination of overburden pressure and vertically-oriented compressive stress due to uplift may have produced localized areas of fractured rock. Sufficient overburden pressure would occur only below some hypothetical minimum burial depth. Where the San Andres has not been buried deeply enough to be fractured, pore pressures within the Clearfork may have been high enough to allow fracturing.

uplift did not reactivate every deeper fault equally. Certain fault blocks could be uplifted higher but be non-prospective because they lack fault-independent closure. The blocks with fault-independent closure could produce from lower elevations or even from the down sides of major reactivated faults. These conclusions suggest two things. First, each major San Andres fold is probably prospective in deeper horizons if reservoir and seal are present because of the parallel nature of the folding. Secondly, deeper exploration should not be ruled out just because the crest of the San Andres fold has been tested dry. Small but commercially attractive prospects may be present that are not reflected in the shallow structure.

Synorogenic Detrital Plays

The Bend, Strawn, and Wolfcamp detrital plays are within the interval that may be cut by faults with post-Permian reactivation. Structural restorations that remove the post-Permian throw may shed light on depositional trends that are masked by the reactivated faulting and folding. Such restorations may help lower reservoir risk by identifying which faults controlled Pennsylvanian and Early Permian synorogenic sedimentation (Figure 10). There may also be some prospects in less-than-obvious locations such as grabens where faults juxtapose reservoirs and seals.

Effects of Fault Reactivation on Trap Style and Remaining Potential of Pre-Woodford Plays

There are several implications for the pre-Woodford structural plays if pre-existing fault blocks have been

reactivated during the Laramide. Winfree (1994; 1995a) presented evidence for as much as 200 feet of post-Permian reactivation of a fault below the Spraberry Trend Area.

The orientations of the faults would determine exactly how they were reactivated and how reactivation affected trap formation. Northwesterly-trending fault zones are dominated by reverse-fault motion because they are perpendicular to maximum Laramide compressive stress so the associated traps are large anticlines and domes. These folds form many of the classic large Permian Basin fields associated with northwesterly-trending fault zones.

The easterly-trending faults are subparallel to the orientation of maximum Laramide compression so they probably experienced some strike-slip motion. These areas appear to consist of numerous small fault blocks. The set of folds associated with easterly-trending fault zones will be monoclines or very small anticlines. The smaller fields with complex structure lie along the easterly-trending fault zones (Figure 11).

One key to exploring for new pre-Woodford fields lies in the fact that fault reactivation has set up two contrasting styles and sizes of pre-Woodford traps. In many areas of the Midland Basin, the large reverse-faulted folds could be imaged with singlefold seismic so the big fields were found early. The easterly-trending fault zones remain relatively unexplored in certain areas. Application of 3-D seismic exploration to these areas could lead to commercial success by minimizing dry-hole risk. There are probably numerous one-or two-well pre-Woodford fields left to be found in the Midland

Basin and Central Basin Platform that could be commercial if they can be properly imaged. Recognition of east-west faults zones that were reactivated could lead to more-efficient selection of areas for 3-D acquisition.

Fault Seal Implications

The easterly-trending faults may have greater risk for fault seal. If strike-slip motion did occur during reactivation, the area adjacent to the fault plane could be highly fractured. The northwesterly-trending faults are more likely to seal because they were oriented normal to the Laramide compression which probably would have kept them closed.

Implications for Ground Water

In many areas of the Midland Basin, surface drainage patterns follow deeper east-west-trending fault zones. The surface expressions of the fault zones may be revealed by localized areas of fractured Cretaceous

Figure 9. Schematic representation of the Seminole field producing horizons. No scale. No wells were used in constructing this diagram but the geometries are based on mapping done by the author and other Exxon geologists.

rocks. High Lonesome Draw (HLD) in Upton County is the surface expression of the fault zone that forms the northern boundary of the HLD block (Winfree 1994; 1995a). The postulated area of greater fracture intensity in the Spraberry lies along this draw. Any fracturing of the Lower Cretaceous would probably be very slight, but it may be sufficient to enhance dissolution of the limestone to produce differential erosion that would create the draw. Unfortunately, the Cretaceous is poorly exposed in High Lonesome Draw so the fracture hypothesis cannot be tested there.

If east-west trending draws represent areas of near-surface fractures, there could be implications for ground water exploration and protection. Obviously, fractures in the sandstones of the Antlers Formation would increase the capacity of water wells. Fractures in the Fredricksburg limestones might provide pathways for dissolution, thus these areas could have additional thicknesses of permeable rock. Recharge could also be greater in these areas if solution channels connect the surface with the Antlers sand. If higher recharge does occur in the areas, the potential for contamination of the Trinity aquifer could be greater.

Figure 10. Schematic diagrams to illustrate the utility of restored cross sections of the synorogenic Pennsylvanian and Early Permian clastics.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Post-Permian folding of the San Andres contributed to the trapping of over 3.5 billion barrels of oil within the Permian Basin region.

2. San Andres lithofacies within the Wasson field indicate that there was no significant topography in the area of the Denver Dome during San Andres deposition.

3. Thinning of the San Andres and younger section over the Denver Dome appears to be the result of differential compaction. Restoration of this section to original thickness increases the height of the Dome. Therefore, differential compaction could not have produced the folding.

4. The Denver Dome was probably formed by post-Permian vertical uplift of deeper fault blocks. This was probably due to early Tertiary reactivation of deeper faults during the time of Laramide compression.

5. Laramide compressive stresses apparently fractured the San Andres where it was buried deeply enough to create elevated pore pressure. Vertical stress caused by uplift of underlying fault blocks may have contributed to higher pore pressure.

6. San Andres and Clearfork waterfloods may be affected by the presence of localized areas of fracture permeability which could lead to inefficient recoveries. Recognition of these areas could lead to reductions in operating expenses.

7. Laramide reactivation of deep faults may have produced areas of highly-fractured shale in the lower part of the Wolfcamp section. Such fractured shales are possible horizontal drilling targets.

8. Reactivated east/west-trending fault zones may be highly prospective for small San Andres and pre-Woodford fields. Identification of these zones could lead to cost-effective acquisition of 3-D surveys.

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